

Market Capitalization as a Percentage of GDP in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "Market Capitalization as a % of GDP" in the Global Innovation Index (GII) measures the total value of a nation's shares relative to its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). It represents the size and maturity of a country's stock market relative to its overall economy. A high percentage indicates a developed and integrated financial market, where companies can raise capital to fund growth and innovation. This variable is important in the context of the GII because it reflects an economy's ability to support innovation through capital markets. A well-functioning stock market allows companies to access financial resources for investments in research and development, acquisition of advanced technologies, and international expansion. In this way, market capitalization can be seen as an indirect indicator of a country's innovation potential. Conversely, a low market capitalization relative to GDP might suggest a limited ability to raise capital through the stock market, potentially hindering the growth of innovative companies. Ultimately, this variable offers a perspective on the role of the financial system in facilitating innovation and global economic competitiveness.

Market Capitalization as a Percentage of GDP in 2022. The data on market capitalization as a percentage of GDP for 2022 show significant differences between countries, reflecting the varying maturity and development of financial markets globally. This variable measures the total value of a nation's shares in relation to its GDP, providing an indicator of the stock market's weight in the overall economy. Hong Kong and South Africa stand out with market capitalizations equivalent to 100% of GDP. These countries have highly developed financial markets that are integrated with the global economy and serve as hubs for international trade and investment. Hong Kong, in particular, benefits from its role as a global financial center, attracting investments from across Asia and serving as a gateway to China. South Africa, the most developed financial market in Africa, demonstrates notable strength despite internal economic challenges. Iran is surprising with a market capitalization level of 96.5% of GDP, reflecting the importance of the local stock market despite international economic sanctions. This figure may be influenced by the limited ability of Iranian companies to access foreign capital, pushing them to rely more on domestic markets. Saudi Arabia (89.2%) and Switzerland (89.1%) also have highly integrated financial markets. Saudi Arabia has benefited from increased openness of its stock market to international investors, while Switzerland is known for the stability and strength of its financial sector. The United States (62.5%) and Canada (51.4%) reflect developed stock markets, although their relative weight compared to GDP is lower than that of the top-ranking countries. The U.S. stock market is among the largest and most liquid globally, with a wide range of industries represented, facilitating corporate financing and capital raising. The United Kingdom (47.2%) and Japan (44.8%) follow with similar market capitalizations, representing mature economies that make extensive use of financial markets to support corporate growth. Among emerging countries, India (32.7%), China (23.5%), and Vietnam (22.4%) show rapidly growing market capitalization levels, although still far from the more developed economies. These countries are increasing their capacity to attract stock market investments through economic reforms and the expansion of the private sector. In many emerging markets, the stock market still represents a relatively small share of the economy, but the growth trend is strong. India, in particular, has seen significant expansion in its financial markets in recent decades, fueled by economic reforms and a

growing middle class. Several countries, such as Italy (9.8%), Turkey (9.5%), and Portugal (10.9%), show a low ratio of market capitalization to GDP. In these cases, this may reflect a financial system less dependent on stock markets and more oriented toward other forms of financing, such as bank credit. Germany (19.6%), despite being one of the strongest economies in the world, has a relatively low market capitalization to GDP ratio. This may be attributed to the predominance of large family-owned companies or the preference for bank financing, a characteristic of the German economic model. At the bottom of the rankings are countries like Ukraine (1.5%), Romania (3.6%), and Nigeria (3.8%), where market capitalization relative to GDP is extremely low. In these cases, the stock market plays a marginal role in the economy, due to political instability, lack of investor confidence, or the absence of solid financial infrastructure. Market capitalization as a percentage of GDP is a key indicator of the maturity and integration of an economy into global financial markets. Countries with high market capitalization tend to have open and dynamic economies, capable of attracting investments and financing innovations. On the other hand, countries with underdeveloped stock markets often face significant challenges in supporting corporate growth and attracting foreign capital. Economic reforms, political stability, and improvements in financial infrastructure could play a crucial role in expanding stock markets in countries with low market capitalization relative to GDP.

Market Capitalization as a Percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2022. The data on market capitalization as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2022 reveal significant changes, both positive and negative, in the financial markets of various countries. This metric measures the total value of a nation's shares relative to its GDP, providing an indication of the stock market's relevance within the economy. Iran recorded the most impressive increase, with a rise of 972.22%, from a market capitalization of 9% of GDP in 2013 to 96.5% in 2022. This change could be the result of an expansion of the local stock market in a context where the country is relatively isolated due to international sanctions, pushing companies to rely more on domestic markets for capital raising. Other countries with strong increases include Vietnam (+224.64%) and Saudi Arabia (+219.71%). Vietnam has benefited from economic reforms and the growth of the private sector, while Saudi Arabia has seen greater openness of its stock market to international investors and has launched ambitious economic diversification plans, as part of the Vision 2030 project. Countries like Japan (+56.10%), Switzerland (+32.20%), and the United States (+25.75%) have seen less dramatic but still significant increases. These countries already possess well-developed stock markets integrated into the global economy. Therefore, the growth in market capitalization is more moderate but still reflects continued expansion and financial stability. In Europe, Belgium (+33.02%) and France (+29.00%) registered notable increases, indicating that their stock markets remain a vital part of their economies. Several emerging and developed economies experienced slight declines in market capitalization relative to GDP. Australia (-1.69%) and Canada (-1.72%) showed slight decreases, likely due to market fluctuations or changes in GDP rather than a real reduction in market capitalization. Italy and China had marginal decreases of -6.52% and -6.82%, respectively. This could reflect a combination of factors, including slower stock market growth relative to GDP or a preference for bank financing over financial markets. Some countries experienced drastic declines in market capitalization. Luxembourg (-53.49%) and Jordan (-60.58%) recorded significant reductions. These declines could be linked to reduced activity in the stock market or economic difficulties affecting investor confidence. Emerging economies such as Sri Lanka (-54.84%), Colombia (-51.92%), and Chile (-44.59%) also saw significant declines. These decreases may be attributed to political instability, economic crises, or difficulties in maintaining the attractiveness of their stock markets for global investors. Ukraine (-79.17%) registered one of the most drastic declines, likely due to political instability and ongoing conflict, which have severely compromised the country's ability to attract investment and support the stock market. The data show that market capitalization relative to GDP can vary dramatically in

response to a wide range of factors, including economic reforms, political stability, market fluctuations, and government policies. While some countries, like Iran, Vietnam, and Saudi Arabia, have seen notable growth, others, like Ukraine, Jordan, and Sri Lanka, have suffered drastic declines. These changes underscore the importance of a stable economic environment and investment-friendly policies to support stock market development and overall economic growth.

Conclusion. On average, the value of market capitalization as a percentage of GDP increased by 0.78% between 2013 and 2022, rising from 23.90% to 24.00%. The top performers include Iran with +972.22%, Vietnam with +224.64%, Saudi Arabia with +219.71%, United Arab Emirates with +99.19%, and Ireland with +84.21%. The worst performers are Sri Lanka with -54.84%, Côte d'Ivoire with -59.35%, Jordan with -60.58%, Serbia with -64.71%, and Ukraine with -79.17%.

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Appendix

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performance	Iran, Islamic Rep.	9	96,5	87,5	972,22
	Vietnam	6,9	22,4	15,5	224,64
	Saudi Arabia	27,9	89,2	61,3	219,71
	United Arab Emirates	12,3	24,5	12,2	99,19
	Ireland	7,6	14	6,4	84,21
Worse Performance	Sri Lanka	15,5	7	-8,5	-54,84
	Cote d'Ivoire	12,3	5	-7,3	-59,35
	Jordan	44,9	17,7	-27,2	-60,58
	Serbia	8,5	3	-5,5	-64,71
	Ukraine	7,2	1,5	-5,7	-79,17